

Puzzle Media On Student Learning Outcomes In Science Learning In Class V Of State Primary School 125138 Pematang Siantar

Winala Sinurat^{1*}, Yanti Arasi Sidabutar², Hetdy Sitio³
Universitas HKBP Nomensen Pematang Siantar, Indonesia

Corresponding Author: Winala Sinurat; winaldasinurat2708@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

Study This examine The Influence of Puzzle Media to Results Study Student on social studies learning in Class V of SD Negeri 125838 Pematang Siantar . Problem in study This are : Students appear less active during the learning process , Teachers have not used learning media optimally so learning is less interesting or less effective , Teachers do not involve students in the learning process so learning is teacher-centred , Low learning outcomes for class V students at SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar . Type research carried out is experiment with approach quantitative , with method Pre-Experiment designs . Population in study This is whole student class v elementary school at 125138 Pematang Siantar . As for who became sample is student class v 125138. Engineering deep data collection study This observation , test results Study And documentation . Technique data analysis consists from Test Normality , Test Hypothesis . Results study show that : the use of puzzle media in social studies learning in class v SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar give influence positive to enhancement results Study increasing students so that give significant influence .

INTRODUCTION

Education is an important means of improving the quality of human resources. So, in order to improve the quality of human resources, activities in the implementation of the learning process must be accompanied by qualified school teaching staff, in the sense of being competent in their field as educational staff so as to support the implementation of learning to improve student learning outcomes as expected by national education goals. want to achieve. As a manager of the learning process, teachers should select and design various learning support components in order to minimize obstacles that exist in the classroom and so that the implementation of learning is more effective. One important component that teachers need to pay attention to in order to carry out effective learning is the selection of media that will be used in the learning process. Choosing the right learning media will give students more understanding of the material because through media it will give students the freedom to use it independently and can also build each student's social skills. Therefore, media is an inseparable part of a process of teaching and learning activities in order to achieve educational goals in general and learning goals at school in particular .

In the learning process, teachers generally only focus on textbooks as the only source of teaching and learning, so that learning activities are characterized by listening, memorizing and summarizing. Therefore, the use of learning media is important because it will provide concrete experiences, attract more students' attention, increase vocabulary and provide meaningful learning experiences for students. So the existence of learning media will create a more conducive learning atmosphere because the process of transforming learning messages from learning sources to students is more enjoyable and effective, which has an impact on the success of the learning process. Because elementary school students are generally still at an age where they enjoy doing activities and have great curiosity.

This is in accordance with the results of observations made in class V of SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar. Where in the learning process students appear to be less active, teachers are not optimal in using learning media so that learning is less interesting or less effective, teachers also do not involve students in the learning process so that learning is teacher-centred. Things like that are what cause students to get bored. So student learning outcomes are low. Low student learning outcomes are an indication that the learning process has not been carried out optimally.

To overcome this problem, new innovations are needed in learning activities, one of which is using learning media that can make students play an active role in learning activities, not feel bored, fed up and enthusiastic about achieving maximum learning results. Therefore, teachers must be clever in choosing learning media and adapting it to the learning material that will be delivered.

Learning outcomes

Learning outcomes are student abilities obtained through teaching and learning activities carried out in the classroom. According to Nurpratiwiningsih (2019:3) learning outcomes are changes in student behavior as a result of the process of teaching and learning activities, in the form of changes in cognitive, affective and psychomotor aspects. According to Rusman (2017:129) who states that learning outcomes are a number of experiences obtained by students which include the cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains. Meanwhile, according to Susanto (2013:5) learning outcomes are the abilities that children gain after going through learning activities.

Several things need to be paid attention to regarding learning outcomes, namely:

- a) Learning outcomes are abilities that are possessed or achieved after students have gone through the learning process
- b) Learning outcomes are student learning achievements
- c) Learning outcomes can be known after the teacher assesses students.

Instructional Media

Learning media in general are tools to help the teaching and learning process. So the media allows students to understand and grasp something easily to remember it for a long time compared to delivering lesson material face to face and in lectures without tools or learning media. Sudjana (2015:196) Learning media are tools or vehicles used by education in the learning process to help convey learning messages. Djamarah (2010: 121) stated that the definition of media is any tool that can be used as a channel for messages to achieve learning goals. Learning media is an intermediary or introduction between the source of the message and the recipient of the message, stimulating thoughts, feelings, attention and will so that they are encouraged and involved in learning Magdalena Ina (2021:8).

Types of Learning Media

- a) Visual Media
- b) Audio Media
- c) Audio Visual Media

The learning media that is considered capable of solving these problems is puzzle media . Puzzle media is a learning medium by assembling messy image pieces into a complete image. This puzzle media really helps teachers to teach social skills to students. In this way, students can share knowledge with each other and entertain students in the class, so that this can influence good student learning outcomes.

Puzzle Media

Puzzle media is a visual medium because puzzle media uses the sense of sight. Puzzle media is one of the media that is more student-centered, where

students are emphasized in finding and solving problems on their own. Yudha (in Putri, Annisa 2022:2) Puzzle media is an image that is divided into image pieces with the aim of sharpening thinking power, training patience, and getting used to sharing skills. Meanwhile, according to Karunia (2022:26), puzzle media is a media that is played by taking it apart. Based on the explanation above, puzzle media is media that can be used by teachers as an aid in learning to attract students' attention by looking for pieces or parts and arranging them according to the provisions.

Through puzzles students can learn and solve problems, can classify objects or images based on size, color, and can adapt to friends. Puzzle media can be done individually, in groups or classically, both inside and outside the classroom. Apart from that, puzzle media can also be called an educational game because it not only plays but also sharpens the brain and trains the speed of the mind and hands. Puzzle media can also stimulate students' thinking and relieve pressure or provide a sense of relaxation in receiving lessons. Apart from that, it can also build social skills as seen from the process of arranging puzzle pieces which is done through discussion.

Objective Puzzle Media

Puzzle media aims to increase student learning creativity. Prima (2016:4) puzzle objectives are as follows:

- a. Foster a sense of togetherness between children.
- b. Practicing strategies in groups to complete the puzzle game , then there is a strategy that must be used.
- c. Practice solving problems together.
- d. Fostering mutual belonging among children. Every child will feel like they belong if they work in groups
- e. Foster mutual respect among children.
- f. Entertaining students in class. Puzzle media is one of the media for entertaining students while receiving material.

Advantages and Disadvantages of Puzzle Media

Like learning media in general, it has advantages and disadvantages. Ayu (2014:80) Puzzle learning media also has the following advantages:

1. Pictures are concrete because through pictures students can see something clearly.
2. With puzzle media, students are able to solve problems because students are required to arrange puzzles until a predetermined puzzle is formed
3. Make students happy in the learning process, because in puzzle media students not only learn to read but students also participate in preparing puzzle media which makes them happy
4. It can make students active and think critically because in puzzle media concentration is needed to be able to complete the puzzle arrangement
5. Students do more activities than teachers.
6. Students are able to work together with their groups
7. Pictures can overcome time limitations, not all objects and objects can be brought into class.

The disadvantages of Media Puzzle are as follows:

- 1) Make students just want to play around
- 2) Lessons are less controlled.
- 3) Students are engrossed in arranging.

Puzzle learning media has various advantages and disadvantages which can be used to improve a learning objective so that the learning objective can be achieved.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Understanding Learning outcomes

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Steps for Implementing Media Puzzle

In implementing puzzle media , steps are needed which can be used in implementing a teaching and learning process so that a directed learning objective can be achieved. Lucia (2010:8) the steps for an educator when teaching using puzzle media are as follows:

1. Puzzle pictures related to the learning material, for example a map of the island of Java, a map of the island of Sumatra, a map of the island of Kalimantan, a map of the island of Bali, a map of the island of Sulawesi and a map of the island of Papua, next,
2. The teacher provides information to students that they are compiling puzzle media
3. Incomplete puzzle pieces
4. To make it more interesting, there is one piece of puzzle picture in each group collected in a cardboard box provided by the teacher, so that students will look for the picture.
5. The puzzle pieces within a predetermined time limit
6. Next, students write down important information on the back of the puzzle
7. The teacher asks students to explain the results of their work in front of their classmates

Based on the explanation above, students not only have to understand the purpose and steps of the puzzle media process , they also have to be directly involved in the learning process activities. Each step in the puzzle media process should take place effectively, therefore students must know how to achieve movement towards loading group decisions.

METHODS

Study Experiment is form research carried out For needs study this . Design on study This is One Group Pre-Test-Post-Test Designing . Design This used Because study This only involve One class that is class experiment started with Pretest before given treatment Then Posttest after given treatment with using Media Puzzle.

Table 1.1 Design Study

Pre-Test	Treatment	Post-test
O1	X	O2

Description :

O1 : test initial (pretest) before using puzzle media

X : puzzle media treatment

O2 : Test final (posttest) after using puzzle media

Population in study This is student class V of SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar , with use Total Sampling technique , so that becomes sample in study This that is student class V, totaling 38 students , consists of of 15 women and 23 men .

Technique data collection used consists from three , viz Observation , Test , Documentation . As for steps taken _ in study This consists on three yep that is stage preparation , stage implementation And stage analyze data. Stage preparation consists on choose material to be used in research , take care of licensing created school _ place study And create a lesson plan that will used . Stage implementation that is carry out activity learning And give pretest And posttest . Next , stage data analysis and reporting form gather And analyze results data management .

Technique data analysis is used For describe the result data Study between pretest And posttest students . As for analysis statistics used For test hypothesis that is technique testing -t test with level significance 0.05. However , before done testing hypothesis moreover formerly done test condition that is test normality with criteria testing that is if $L_o < L_{table}$ with level significant 0.005 then the data is said to be normally distributed .

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Results

Step initial work done by researcher is do validation of the question instrument (Pretest And Posttest), before used And next with give treatment use of puzzle media for know the influence of puzzle media on results Study student on social studies learning.

Description of student learning outcomes before being given treatment (pretest results). Based on results analysis carried out there is The highest pretest score was 60 and the lowest score was 36. The average pretest score was 49.58. There are no students who have scores above the KKM. All students have scores below the KKM, namely 38 students.

Description of student learning outcomes after being given treatment (posttest results) Based on results analysis carried out n the highest score on the posttest was 96, while the lowest score was 72. The average on the posttest was 85.37. There were 38 students who obtained scores above the KKM. The learning outcomes in the posttest were better than the pretest.

Normality test

The normality test is included to determine whether the data used is distributed or not. This Normality Test uses the help of the SPSS 21 program with the Kolmogrow-Smimov program .

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a		
	Statistic	df	Sig.
PRETEST	.139	38	.062
POSTTEST	.123	38	.153

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Based on table above, it can be seen that for a sample of 38 students, the sig shows the pretest value on the normality test, namely 0.062. Meanwhile, the posttest value for the normality test was 0.153. Based on the results obtained, it can be concluded that the pretest and posttest data used were normally distributed because the significant results obtained were > 0.05 .

Hypothesis testing

Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Paired Sample 1 Posttest - Pretest	35.78947	7.88827	1.27965	33.19666	38.38228	27,968	37	,000

Based on the table above, it shows $t_{hitung} = 27.968$ with a significant level (2 Tailed) 0.000, significant probability < 0.05 . $t_{hitung} > t_{tabel} = 27.968 > 2.026$ then H_0 is rejected and H_a accepted. This explanation shows that there is an influence of Puzzle Media on the learning outcomes of class V students in social studies at SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar .

Discussion

Pretest results , the average student learning outcome score was 49.58 with all students scoring below the KKM. Looking at the existing percentages, it can be said that the level of student learning outcomes before using Puzzle Media was relatively low.

Furthermore, the average posttest score was 85.37. So after using Media Puzzle students have better learning outcomes than before using Media Puzzle . After carrying out the pretest and posttest normality test . After the normality test has been fulfilled, proceed to hypothesis testing. From the student test results are obtained $t_{hitung} > t_{tabel} = 27,968$ and t_{tabel} amounting to 0,028. Thus $t_{hitung} > t_{tabel} = 27.968 > 2.028$ which means H_0 it is accepted which indicates that there is an influence of Puzzle Media on student learning outcomes with normal learning.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

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